

Integrated Promotion and Regional Cooperation for Sustainable Tourism Development: A Case Study in Padang Panjang Regency West Sumatra, Indonesia

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Tourism sector is the dominant sector in Padang Panjang Regency West Sumatra province of Indonesia. Local governments have a serious attention to make this sector as the basis for local economic development. The main problem is what is the most appropriate strategy to develop the tourism sector as a leading sector to encourage economic growth in accordance with objective conditions of the region.

This study aims to determine the most appropriate strategies in accordance with the objective conditions of Padang Panjang Regency, using deductive and inductive processes. The results showed that the most appropriate strategy to develop tourism sector in Padang Panjang Regency is establishing connectivity and cooperation with the surrounding area, through travel packages and integrated promotion by involving local community, academics, and businessman.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Tourism industry is the third largest industries that contribute to the gross national income in Indonesia, and is expected to continue due to the increasing of public welfare. Along with the government's efforts to improve the welfare of the community, each regency is expected to have a base of economic development to increase public welfare that is suitable with potential resources owned.

Padang Panjang Regency is one the famous area in West Sumatra, because it has some cultural sites, such as *minangese culture center* and *thawalib education center*, one of the oldest religion education system in Indonesia, and the most popular cultural attractions in West Sumatra [1]. Padang Panjang Regency is also a place for the international event "Tour de singkarak", very popular event of world bicycle racing, the second famous of world racing after Paris-Dakkar tour. This region can also serve as a connector for its surrounding tourism areas, such as Kota Gadang, Japanese Caves in Bukittinggi, Lake Singkarak, and Lake Maninjau.

The main problem is that the potential tourism sector still can not be fully utilized to support local economic development. The purpose of this research is to select the most appropriate strategy to develop sustainable tourism sector as the basis of the economic development for the local community according to real condition.

2. LITERATUR REVIEW

Tourism sector is the third largest industry that contribute to the Gross National Income in Indonesia. This sector will be always prospective in the future due to higher public welfare [2]. Currently, Indonesia's tourism sector contributes to approximately 4% of the total economy. In 2019, the Indonesian government wants to increase double to 8% of GDP, an ambitious target which implies that within the next 4 years, and the number of visitors should be increased to approximately 20 million [3]. To realize this expectation, the government will focus on improving infrastructures (including information technology infrastructure and communications), access, health and hygiene and also improve the online promotion campaign with the support of information technology. Infrastructure is the main

problem in Indonesia, it's impact is not only increases logistics costs but also making less attractive of investment climate, and reduces the tourist trips to tourist destinations area [2].

According to [4], Tourism sector has a major role in providing jobs. In the last 10 years the number of tourism sector employment continued to rise; estimated in 2015 reached 15.1% of the total workforce. The government expects in 2017 the number of employment in the tourism sector of 12.4 million people with a revenue of IDR 182 trillion [2].

To increase the number of tourists, especially foreign tourists, local governments are encouraged to develop tourism sector in accordance with existing objective conditions. Geographically, Padang Panjang Regency which is located between Bukittinggi Regency and Tanah Datar Regency is an excellent potential for the development of tourism industry. The main tourist attraction in Padang Panjang is cultural tourism: Plate dance and Thawalib education system, [5].

Tourism destinations are areas or geographic regions that differ in one or more administrative regions include: tourist attraction, tourism facilities, accessibility, community as well as tourists are interrelated and complementary to the realization of tourism activities. While tourist attractions is anything that has a unique, convenience, and value in the form of the wealth of diversity of natural, cultural and man-made results that were targeted or tourist visits, [6]. Tourism produces direct local impacts on air, water, soil and biota; and indirect impacts from manufacture and transport of material items. Impacts derive from atmospheric emissions, solid and liquid wastes, and consumption of water, energy and materials, [7,8,9]. There are three main tourist activities: something to buy, something to learn and something to do, [10]. Tourism also can support conservation through private reserves, communal conservancies, and contributions to public protected areas, but only under some circumstances, and with associated environmental costs, [11,12]. Negative impact of tourist activities are air pollution, solid waste, land degradation, shortage of water resources. Water, especially fresh water is one of most critical natural resources. The tourism industry generally overuses water resources for hotels,

swimming pool, golf courses and personal uses of water for tourists, [13], so the sustainability of tourism development threatened, [14].

Sustainable tourism development guidelines and management practices are applicable to all forms of tourism in all types of destinations, including mass tourism and the various niche tourism segments. Sustainability principles refer to the environmental, economic, and socio-cultural aspects of tourism development, and a suitable balance must be established between these three dimensions to guarantee its long-term sustainability, [15]. It mean that sustainable tourism should (1) optimal use of environmental resources, (2) respect to social cultural and traditional value, (3) providing economics benefit to local people. In the context of sustainable tourism, the main indicator sustainability of a destination, [16,17]. Thus, sustainable tourism is responsible tourism which minimal impact on the environment and culture, [18].

Local communities involvement have a big role in developing sustainable tourism, [19,20], one of the most important roles of local communities on involvement stages of tourism development is the provision of culinary and accesories, support and participate in the development of cultural attraction, [10]. Minangese social culture is one of the most tourist attraction in Padang Panjang City, [21]. Minangese is a special dance from Padang Panjang Regency, played by the public by bringing a plate, this dance became the main show every official event. Sustainable tourism development has three key component: (1) Environmentally, has a low impact on natural resources, particularly in protected areas. (2). Socially and culturally acceptable, it does not harm the social structure or culture of the community where it is located, (3) Economically feasible, it contributes to the economic well being of the community, generating sustainable and equitable income for local communities and as many other stakeholders as possible.

3. METHODOLOGY

Method used was system approach by combining inductive and deductive process. The inductive process using Soft System Methodology or SSM, [22]. While deductive process using SOSM (System of System Methodology). SOSM is a systems approach which can be used as a basis for decision-making, [23] some of methods usually used in SOSM are Interpretative Structural Modeling

(ISM), Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), SAST (Strategic Assumption Surfacing and Testing (SAST), Exponential Rank Method (ERM) and Decession Matrix (DM), [24,25]. To determine the most suitable strategy inaccordance with objective condition, SOSM method chosen was ERM. Generally method used as shown below.

Fig. 1. Method of study

SOSM: System of System Methodology

ERM: Exponential Rank Method

IOM: Intermediate Objective Map

SSM: System of System Methodology

RP: Rich Picture

RD: Root Definition

ELT: Experience Based Learning Theory

ERM used to select the most suitable alternative in accordance with real condition. RP and RD used for describing interrelated between aspects and actors. IOM to describes claim which related to the development of tourism sector, and PAM to identify important activities should be done in order to develop sustainable tourism sector. Experiential learning thery (ELT) is system approach based logical thinking process [26], based on critical thinking and looking for some important indicators, [24].

Data collection was done through expert discussion, which includes practitioners, academics, policy makers, businesses and local community leaders.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result of inductive by ERM analysis showed that regional cooperation is the highest rank

(395.78), followed by integrated promotion (389.12). This mean that the development of surrounding area especially Bukit Tinggi and Tanah Datar Regency, is the key for tourist attraction in Padang Panjang. Because there is only one road to Padang Panjang Regency through Bukit Tinggi or Tanah Datar Regency. The ERM analysis showed in Table 1.

Regional cooperation means establishing a connection especially road infrastructure, travel information, travel packages and the carrying capacity of the environment. Joint travel package development is very important, so tour guides will making Padang Panjang Regency as a travel package in Western Sumatra.

Government has been split into three roads, national roads built funded by government, provincial roads funded by the Government of provincial and district roads financed by the district government. Transport connections between and towards Padang Panjang should be financed by the provincial government because it connecting two or more districts within a province. Therefore collaboration with provincial governments is also important. Integrated promotion especially with the surrounding area is

very important but actually this is the main problem between regions, due to the competition of attract tourists. The results of this study showed without integrated promotion, natural beauty and unique culture will not be an attraction for tourists.

Based on deductive analysis by ERM method, can be built claims as the following IOM (Fig. 2).

IOM analysis showed that promotion and regional cooperation as a critical success factor depend on government policy and government regulation (*necessary condition*), which mean creativity of local government leader is very critical determining the success of tourism promotion. Government regulation (Act no 10/2009 and Act No 23/2014) was the basis of the local government policy for local economic development based on the potential of local resources, [1]. In order to develop sustainable tourism, IOM in Fig. 2 also showed that public participation, micro finance, infrastructure, touris industries and HRD (human resources development) have a crucial role. If pre-conditions are not met, the sustainability of tourism sector in Padang Panjang will be threatened.

**Table 1. Exponential rank method
Tourism area development strategy in Padang Panjang Regency**

No.	Component	Critical level	Level of relatedness				Total value	Rank
			Social aspect	Economics aspect	Cultural aspect	Political aspect		
1	Infrastructure	2.6	24.09	52.87	27.95	32.17	137.08	7
2	HRD	2.6	36.76	47.10	36.76	27.95	148.56	6
3	Government policy	1.6	9.94	12.30	9.19	17.58	49.01	9
4	Public participation	2.8	124.43	71.73	112.38	63.34	371.89	3
5	Center of Minangese culture /Center of Excelence	2.8	42.01	80.81	80.81	48.50	252.14	4
6	Regional cooperation	3.0	110.59	110.59	110.59	64.00	395.78	1
7	The role of Tourism Industry	2.4	35.02	43.15	47.59	24.63	150.38	5
8	Integrated Promotion	2.8	124.03	71.73	150.95	42.01	389.12	2
9	Tourism Education Center	2.4	38.96	24.63	35.02	23.10	121.71	8

Fig. 2. IOM analysis result

Inductive process begins with the formulation of root definition (RD) as a description of linkages between aspects and actors in the development of tourism. The results of expert discussion and analysis of actual conditions root definition can be formulated as follow:

1. *Sustainable tourist development by involving local people, research institution, tourism businessman and cooperation with surrounding region to build integrated promotion for increasing tourists visit.*
2. *Tourism sector development that environmentally friendly, improving social welfare of local community, and local government income, and encourage of local economic development.*

By using the above definition, rich picture can be described as (Fig. 3).

Some of important activities to ensure sustainable tourism sector development in Padang Panjang Regency based on the previous analysis, as shown in the following PAM (Fig. 4).

Integrated promotion with surrounding areas is the key activities, by involving local community, academics and businessman. To ensure each activity well running, it should be defined Key

Performance Indicators (KPI) and monitoring and evaluation systems, as well as the supervision in order to the achievement in line with the targets. Governance role of government is very crucial, to ensure the sustainability of the tourism sector development program, due to the change of local leadership, it is necessary to build a strategic plan in the next 5 years.

There are some important aspects which can be formulated from deductive and inductive process through convergence experience based learning theory (ELT) approach, [27] as shown in Fig. 5.

Sustainable economic development paradigm [27] is balancing of environmental, economic, and social features. This mean that the beneficiary of tourism sector development should not only for businesses, but local people should be able to take economic and social benefits, and their environment conserved. This reserch result in line with previous research [28] that the local community would support if they get economic benefits. These will create a sense of belonging for the local people, so the sustainability of the tourism area will be maintained by local people. Based on previos analysis action plan formulation as shown Fig. 6.

Fig. 3. Rich Picture sustainable tourism development in Padang Panjang Regency

Fig. 4. Purposeful Activity Model (PAM) analysis of sustainable tourism development in Padang Panjang Regency

Fig. 5. Convergence of deductive and inductive process

Fig. 6. Action plan of 3 years tourism development in Padang Panjang

5. CONCLUSION

There are four important aspects should be done by the local government of Padang Panjang Regency to develop the tourism sector: (1) Integrated promotion (2) Public involvement (3) regional cooperation, and (4) tourism information system development. The most interesting minangese cultures in Padang Panjang Regency are Plate Dance and Thowalib Education System. The best strategy to ensure

sustainability of tourism sector in Padang Panjang Regency is integrated promotion and regional cooperation with surrounding areas by involving local community, academics, businessman and decission makers.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The weakness of this study in practical perspective was not able to determine what is the most appropriate regional cooperation

according to real condition in building a tourist area in west sumatra, and therefore need to further study using appropriate methods to know their respective roles.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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